

CURRENT ISSUES OF ORGANIZING WORKS ON PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, what should be paid attention to and how to organize a physical education lesson for students, as well as the sensitive periods of the student's physical abilities and the ways of their development are described.

Many experts in the field of physical education and sports are interested in the development of children's movement abilities and the problem of determining the developmental effect of physical exercises on the children's body. This interest has been going on for a century. Why is it considered one of the most complex problems?

At present, there are up to 18 types of human endurance, about 20 special coordination abilities that are manifested in various specific movement activities (cyclic, acyclic), close coordination abilities that are manifested in a unique way (balance, rhythm, reaction, aiming, etc.), in addition to this, various forms of flexibility, strength and speed skills are distinguished. When it comes to exercise, many questions arise, such as:

- what movement skills need to be developed, when and are they all necessary?
- to what extent do they depend on genetic factors and can they be increased by means of exercises?
- what should these abilities be called: "movement abilities", "motor" or "physical" abilities?
- Are "movement abilities" and "physical qualities" synonymous concepts?
- how are motor skills classified?
- are there sensitive periods of skill development?
- What are the main tools and methods needed to develop skills?
- How should you plan materials for the development of motor skills during the year, quarter, week?

Theoreticians have puzzled over these problems a lot, and it is especially difficult for a practicing teacher to correctly evaluate them.

Using the research of a number of scientists and practitioners, "Why do you need to work on motor skills regularly?" we will try to find an answer to the question.

Good physical fitness is the basis of high work ability in all activities (work, study, sports), and it is determined by the level of development of basic physical qualities. The main type of activity in children of junior school age is mental activity, which requires constant concentration and being in a sitting position for a long time. This requires a much higher level of strength and endurance of the respective muscle groups.

If the student has strong, durable, fast muscles, the process of mastering basic movement activities will be more successful.

A high level of development of physical abilities is an important component of the state of health.

The development of movement abilities helps to solve socially determined tasks: comprehensive and harmonious development of the individual, achieving the organism's resistance to social and ecological conditions, increasing the adaptive, i.e. adaptation characteristics of the organism. It contributes to the growth of physical and mental work capacity, ensures the fuller realization of human creative forces for the benefit of society.

Different concepts are used to name abilities related to movement: physical, movement, motor, psychophysical, etc. these concepts and terms reflect the unique aspects of the sciences that created them. For example, in the theory and methodology of physical education and sports, the concepts of movement and physical abilities are used, in biomechanics, the term motor abilities is used, etc.

The words development, improvement, education are often used in relation to motor skills. How can these terms be used correctly and literately? It is not easy to distinguish between development and improvement, because in the process of improvement, the development of movement skills occurs gives Education is related to a whole person, his moral-volitional, spiritual and personal qualities. Intuitions themselves say that abilities are not trained, but developed.

It is accepted to call innate morphofunctional qualities physical qualities, due to which physical activity fully manifests itself in purposeful movement activity. Basic physical attributes include strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, and agility.

In general, movement abilities can be defined as individual characteristics that determine the level of human movement capabilities. But the color of the eyes or the desire to sleep more in the morning - these are also considered individual characteristics. Our task is to consider individual characteristics (TSS, anthropometric data, speed of nervous processes, etc.) that affect the efficiency of human activity.

Various innate (hereditary) anatomic physiological targets are based on different development of abilities (Lyakh 1996):

- anatomical-morphological characteristics of the brain and nervous system (characteristics of nervous processes - strength, mobility, restraint; individual variants of the nervous system);
- physiological characteristics (cardiovascular, respiratory system characteristics);
- biological (biological oxidation, metabolism, strength of muscle contractions) characteristics;
- characteristics of the body system (body length and weight, mass of muscle and fat tissue);
- characteristics of chromosomes (genes).

The development of motor skills is influenced by psychodynamic targets (temperament, character or character, control of mental processes and self-control features).

When thinking about a person's abilities, they judge him not according to his achievements in any activity, but according to how quickly and easily he acquires such skills and qualifications.

Movement abilities are manifested and developed during the implementation of activities. It is enough to improve the methods of upbringing and education, to choose a reasonable combination of tools and forms, and immediately the limits of the development of abilities will expand even more. Accurate information about the level of development of motor skills can be obtained using certain tests.

In modern literature, the terms "physical qualities" and "movement abilities" are used. However, their meanings are not the same. In general, movement abilities can be defined as individual characteristics that determine the level of human movement possibilities (Lyakh 1996).

Physical abilities are relatively stable innate and functional characteristics of organs and structures in the body that appear during life, their interaction determines the effectiveness of performing movement activities. Congenital characteristics are determined by the relevant signs, and those that appear during life are determined by the social and ecological environment in which a person lives.

The realization of abilities in movement activities represents the development characteristics and level of functional capabilities of certain organs and structures in the body. Therefore, the ability to move separately cannot fully express the corresponding physical quality. Only a relatively constant set of movement abilities, which determine the solution of the movement task, shows one or another quality. For example, it is impossible to think about endurance, which is a physical quality of a person based on the ability to maintain a single speed of movement in a submaximal power mode. It is possible to say something about this quality only when the sum of all movement abilities ensures the ability to maintain the speed of activity in different modes.

So we conclude:

- Movement skills are the basis of the development of physical qualities.
- The development of motor skills is determined by the targets of innate abilities.
- Physical qualities are developed by solving various movement tasks, and to develop movement skills, it is necessary to perform movement activities.

LP While considering the concepts of "physical qualities" and "physical abilities", Matveev refers to the relationship between the concepts of "qualities" and "characteristics" in philosophy. The sum of features represents the quality. Or, in the theory and method of physical education, the sum of movement abilities represents physical quality. "Motion quality is a concept that reflects the qualitative accuracy of various movement abilities."

In this way, until the action activity begins, abilities are masked, unrealized, in the form of targets of anatomical-physiological abilities, or in the form of hidden opportunities, which, if appropriate conditions are not created, can remain as a mere opportunity. Abilities appear and develop in the process of performing one or more activities, but this is always a combined

effect of genetic and environmental factors. The duration of competitions held in various sports is determined by the rules of international competitions.

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